

URI, URL, URN

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You most likely already know what a **URL**—or web address—is, as most people who have ever used a web browser have had to type or click on one to access a webpage. What you might not know, though, is that a URL is a type of **URI**, and also that you have already encountered many **URNs** without realizing it. In the following paragraphs, you will find an explanation of these three concepts, the differences between them, and why understanding them is important.

Resources Need to be Identified

In order to retrieve a resource on the internet—whether it is a website, a document, a PDF, an image, a video, or audio—you need to identify it, much like a government needs to identify its citizens. For example, ‘James Smith’ is the most common full name in America. While there may be many people with this name, each individual can be uniquely identified by their Social Security Number (SSN). The SSN ensures that one James Smith can be distinguished from another. If the governments wants instead to send a document to one James Smith, it can use their mailing address, since neither the name, nor the SSN would be enough for locating that particular John Smith.

Now, you are working on a project on Heritage, and you need to read a book titled *Methods and Methodologies in Heritage Studies* by Rachel King and Trinidad Rico. There are likely many books and articles about Heritage studies, but this one can be uniquely identified by its **ISBN** (International Standard Book Number). The ISBN for this book is 978-1-80008-381-3, which is a unique number that helps to identify it. Think of it like a person’s Social Security Number—it ensures that there’s no mix-up between this book and any other.

To access a digital copy, you would use a website address, such as `https://uclpress.co.uk/book/methods-and-methodologies-in-heritage-studies/`. This works like a mailing address—it tells your browser exactly where to go to find the book online.

Now, what if you’re looking for the book’s digital version but the webpage changes over time? This is where the **DOI** (Digital Object Identifier) comes in. The DOI for this book is `doi:10.14324/111.9781800083790`. A DOI is a permanent identifier that remains the same even if the book’s online location changes. You can use a DOI to locate a resource, just like a web address does.

Congratulations! You’ve just encountered URNs, URLs, and URIs. But what exactly is the difference between them? If both a DOI and an ISBN serve as unique identifiers, how do they differ? And how does a DOI compare to a URL? To answer these questions, let’s dive into a bit of technical mumbo-jumbo.

URIs

At the most basic level, a **URI** (Uniform Resource Identifier) is a compact sequence of characters used to identify abstract or physical resources on the internet. A URI can reference any entity—whether abstract, such as the moral and aesthetic concept of purity, or concrete, like the Colosseum in Rome. The structure of URIs is defined in RFC3986, a normative specification published by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) in January 2005.

Generally, URIs follow a common pattern that includes five components: **scheme**, **authority**, **path**, **query**, and **fragment**. These elements are hierarchical, meaning the order in which they appear matters.

```
foo://example.com:8042/over/there?name=ferret#nose
  \_/  \-----/ \-----/ \-----/ \_/
   |      |           |           |           |
  scheme authority path query fragment
```


A **URN** (Uniform Resource Name) identifies a resource but provides no immediate mean to access it. As exemplified above, typical URNs are the ISBN or the ISSN. From a technical perspective:

- A DOI, in its base form, is a URN, a unique identifier not resolvable by design.
- When a DOI is resolved (e.g., via `https://dx.doi.org/`), it effectively functions as a URL.

In summary:

- The book's ISBN is a URN (not resolvable by design).
- The book's DOI is a URN (resolvable by design).
- The book's webpage is a URL (tied to its current location).

All of these are types of URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers).

So, are there URIs that are not URLs or URNs? Technically, **no**. In the formal specification of URIs (RFC3986, linked above), all URIs fall into one of these two categories. So, every URI you encounter will be a URL or URN, or possibly a combination of the two. However, in common usage, you might hear the term “URI” used more generally, especially when discussing schemes or identifiers that don't fully fall into the categories of URL or URN. But from a technical standpoint, any URI you encounter will be a URL or a URN.

You might wonder what is the point of having the URN `doi:10.14324/111.9781800083790` and the resolved URL `https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781800083790`. Wouldn't `https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781800083790` be enough? The URN and the URL serves different purposes, and each has its distinct role in the broader ecosystem of digital resource identification and retrieval.

Special Guest: IRIs

URIs use exclusively the American Standard Code for Information Interchange (ASCII, pronounced / æski /) character encoding system. This system includes the Latin alphabet without accents, along with a few punctuation symbols (A-Z, a-z, 0-9, - . _ ~). ASCII has been in use since 1963 and is universally supported across all computer systems, ensuring compatibility and preventing encoding issues.

Internationalized Resource Identifiers (IRIs) were introduced in 2005 as part of RFC 3987. They were created to allow web addresses (URIs) to include characters from a wider range of languages beyond the ASCII character set. While URIs were limited to a small set of characters (A-Z, a-z, 0-9, and a few symbols), IRIs support Unicode characters, making it possible to use languages such as Japanese, Arabic, Chinese, and many others directly in URLs. For example, in a typical URI, you would see a web address like `https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zeus`, but with IRIs, you could have a web address like `https://ja.wikipedia.org/wiki/` for the Japanese Wikipedia page about Zeus, which includes Katakana characters.

However, older systems or protocols that do not support IRIs still require percent-encoding for compatibility. This converts the Unicode characters into a format that only uses ASCII characters, which helps older systems interpret them. For instance, the IRI `https://ja.wikipedia.org/wiki/` would be encoded as `https://ja.wikipedia.org/wiki/%E3%82%BC%E3%82%A6%E3%82%B9`.

Key Takeaways

URIs are the backbone of the internet, ensuring unique identification, access, interconnectivity, and data exchange across systems. Without them, the web wouldn't exist as we know it.

In the **Semantic Web**, precise identification is essential. The term “semantic” implies that we want the web to reason and infer meaning from data. For this to work, information must be interconnected and unambiguously identifiable. Take *The Night Watch* as an example—one of Rembrandt's most famous paintings and a masterpiece of the Dutch Golden Age. In the 17th century, a copy was commissioned from Gerrit Lundens. But look at how many more unrelated resources go by the same name.